

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

INCIDENCE OF DEFICIENCY OF VITAMIN-D AND ITS ASSOCIATION WITH THE SEVERITY OF LIVER DAMAGE IN THE PATIENTS SUFFERING FROM HCV INFECTION

Dr Muhammad Jawad, Dr Sana Ullah Khan, Dr Hafiz M. Hamza Arshad
House Officers, CMH Lahore

Article Received: April 2020

Accepted: May 2020

Published: June 2020

Abstract:

Objective: Role of Vitamin-D is very important in different infectious diseases. Among these diseases, infections of the liver are highly distinct. This research work was carried out for the determination of the status of Vitamin-D in patients with HCV infection and healthy controls.

Methodology: We conducted this research work on 74 patients at CMH Lahore from August 2019 to December 2019. Fifty-one patients were positive for hepatitis C RNA-PCR. Additionally, we recruited 23 persons without any liver complication as healthy controls. We performed the HCV RNA-PCR by ARTUS & HCV QS-RGQ V-1. The measurement of the levels of Vitamin-D was carried out by chemiluminescence. We used SPSS V.23 for the statistical analysis of the collected information.

Results: Average Vitamin-D level was low in the patients of HCV infection in both compensated & decompensated cirrhotic patients (26.850 ng/mL and 20.650 ng/mL, correspondingly) in comparison to the subjects of healthy controls (30.410 ng/mL). This research work showed sub-optimal Vitamin-D level in 76.50% patients of HCV infection. Insufficiency of Vitamin-D (21.0-29.0 ng/mL) was prevalent among controls (47.80%) as well as in the patients of HCV infection (39.20%) ($P < 0.0010$). Additionally, levels of Vitamin-D displayed an inverse relationship with severe conditions of the liver complications as 55.20% patients of decompensated cirrhosis were suffering from the deficiency of Vitamin-D as compared to the 13.60% patients with Vitamin-D deficiency in the group of compensated cirrhosis. ($P < 0.00010$).

Conclusion: Sub-optimal Vitamin-D levels are much prevalent in patients suffering from HCV infection in comparison to their controls. There is a direct association of the Vitamin-D deficiency with the disease severity.

KEYWORDS: Cirrhosis, Compensated, Decompensated, Prevalent, Deficiency, Hepatitis, HCV, Infection, Vitamin-D.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Muhammad Jawad,
House Officers, CMH Lahore

QR code

Please cite this article in press Muhammad Jawad et al., *Incidence Of Deficiency Of Vitamin-D And Its Association With The Severity Of Liver Damage In The Patients Suffering From HCV Infection.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(06).

INTRODUCTION:

HCV infection is an important issue of health, and it is life-threatening because of its severe associated complications. HCV infection is responsible for more than 70,000 mortalities every year with diseases of more than 170 million population of the world [1]. In Pakistan, the rate of incidence of HCV infection is very high, and it plays a very important role in various diseases of the liver. So, it is a national priority to take preventive measures to reduce the incidence of this complication in the whole world [2]. It is a well-acknowledged fact that deficiency of Vitamin-D has an association with many infectious diseases. Among these diseases, infections of the liver are highly distinct. The serum concentration of the Vitamin-D has an inverse association with the severity of liver diseases and advancement in the cirrhosis of the liver. There are many research works which state the significant relationship of levels of 25-hydroxy Vitamin-D in HCV infection and serum [3]. Up to 90.0%, Vitamin-D is regained from UVB (Ultra Violet B) irradiation induction in the body skin. Another amount is derived from the supplements and diet [4, 5]. Milk, eggs and fish are a good source of Vitamin-D3. There is no production of Vitamin-D2 in human beings, and it is mostly derived from plants. Both Vitamin-D2&D3 are inactive physiologically. There is an occurrence of Vitamin-D activation in the hydroxylation reaction [6].

Estimation of the level of Vitamin-D is carried out by the measurement of the concentration of both types of Vitamin-D in serum. The guidelines of Endocrine Society of Clinical Practice on the frequency of Vitamin-D defines deficit as <20.0 ng/mL, insufficiency as 21.0 to 29.0 ng/mL and sufficiency as >30.0 ng/mL of serum 25.0-OH-D [4]. The rate of incidence of infections because of HCV in Lahore is about 22.0% which is much threatening as compared to the other areas of the country [7]. So, there is a need to take timely, aggressive preventive measures to mitigate this complication. As there is a strong association of the deficiency of Vitamin-D to the infection of HCV, hence this research work was conducted to determine the Vitamin-D status in the patients of HCV.

METHODOLOGY:

To determine the relationship between the status of Vitamin-D and HCV infection, the recruitment of 74 participants carried out from August 2019 to December 2019. We used the standard empirical approach to the recruitment of these patients [8]. This transverse research work was carried out in CMH Lahore. The ethical committee of the hospital permitted to conduct this research work. We took the written consent from every patient after describing them the purpose of this research work. We divided the patients into two groups; a group of patients with compensated cirrhosis (22) with positive HCV RNA-PCR but without ascites and group of patients of decompensated cirrhosis (29) with positive HCV RNA-PCR and ascites as well as other signs of decompensated cirrhosis as hematemesis, jaundice.

Also, we selected 23 healthy controls in this research work. All these participants were without known chronic complication and any supplementation of Vitamin-D for last six months. The extraction of the HCV-RNA was carried out by the utilization of the QIA symphony SP automation work-station by QIAGEN. We used the enhanced chemiluminescence method for the measurement of the concentration of the Vitamin-D level. SPSS V.23 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information. We presented the categorical variables in percentages and frequencies, whereas the presentation of the quantitative variables was carried out in averages and standard deviations. For the comparison of the differences in groups, the application of χ^2 tests and Kruskal-Wallis tests were performed for categorical variables. We used the Students T-test for the analysis of the continuous variables.

RESULTS:

A sum of 74 subjects got recruitment in this research work. Based on clinical examinations and anti-HCV titers, the classification of the participants was carried out into a group of healthy controls (n: 23) and patients with HCV infection (n: 51). The categorization of the HCV group was carried out in 2 sub-groups; compensated cirrhosis (c-HCV) (n: 22) & decompensated cirrhosis (d-HCV) (n: 29) as presented in Table-1.

Table-I: Demographic and Clinical Parameter of HCV And Control Subjects

Characteristics	Control (n=23)	Compensated Cirrhosis (n=22)	Decompensated Cirrhosis (n=29)	P-value
Age (Mean, range)	36.09(20-50)	48.68(29-65)	50.69 (35-65)	< 0.001
Gender (Male/Female)	9/14	10/12	10/19	0.729
Joint Pains (No/Yes)	6/17	02/20	9/20	0.166
Ascites (No/Yes)	22/1	22/0	29/0	< 0.001
Jaundice (No/Yes)	23/0	21/1	6/23	< 0.001
Hematemesis (No/Yes)	23/0	20/2	12/17	< 0.001
Blood Transfusion (No/Yes)	19/4	14/8	15/14	0.068
HCV RNA PCR QL (No/Yes)	23/0	0/22	0/29	< 0.001
Serum 25(OH)D ng/mL	30.413	26.85	20.6483	< 0.001

The range of the age of the participants was 20 to 65 years. The subjects of the control group were younger as compared to the patients of HCV infection ($P < 0.0010$). The average age of the healthy controls was 36.09 ± 9.125 years. The average age of the HCV infected patients with c-HCV was 48.68 ± 12.442 years, and for the patients with d-HCV as 50.690 ± 8.410 years. Majority of the subjects in both control and patient groups were females as 60.20% & 60.80% correspondingly. But this disparity was insignificant based on sex ($P = 0.7290$). We observed no significant differences in different groups of study for joint pain ($P = 0.1660$) as there is the insufficiency of Vitamin-D in the normal population. As far as biochemical parameters are concerned, there was an important change in hematemesis, jaundice and activity of blood transfusion ($P < 0.0680$) (Table-1). There was low 25.0 (OH) Vitamin-D in the patients of HCV as compared to the subjects of the control group (Table-1, Figure-1).

In the sub-groups of HCV patients, there was no significant difference in the level of Vitamin-D between healthy controls and patients of c-HCV ($P = 0.1170$) in comparison with level between healthy controls and d-HCV ($P < 0.0010$). When the classification of the distribution of the Vitamin-D was carried out following the guidelines of Endocrine Society of Clinical Practice, the majority of the subjects of this research work were present with insufficiency of Vitamin-D level. On average, the group of healthy controls scarcely falls in the category of sufficient Vitamin-D level. In contrast, the patients of the c-HCV group were present with insufficient Vitamin-D level, and patients of the d-HCV group were much low in the deficient category of Vitamin-D. There was an association of insufficiency and deficiency of Vitamin-D between healthy controls and patients of HCV and also in its sub-groups ($P < 0.00010$ for every group and $P = 0.030$ control versus patients of HCV) (Table-2, Figure-2).

Out of 51 patients, only 23.50% of subjects were present with normal Vitamin-D level, 37.30% of patients were present with deficiency of Vitamin-D, and there was the inefficiency of Vitamin-D in 39.20% patients. In HCV sub-groups, we observed a lack of Vitamin-D in the d-HCV group as 55.20% in comparison with the c-HCV group as 13.60%.

Table-II: Frequency Distribution of HCV-Infected Patients and Healthy Controls with Vitamin-D Stratum

Vitamin-D stratum	Control (n=23) n (%)	HCV (n= 51) n (%)	Compensated Cirrhosis (n= 29) n (%)	Decompensated Cirrhosis (n =22) n (%)
Deficient	2 (8.7%)	19 (37.3%)	3 (13.6%)	16(55.2%)
Insufficient	11(47.8%)	20 (39.2%)	12 (54.5%)	8(27.6%)
Normal	10 (43.5%)	12 (23.5%)	7(31.8%)	5(17.2%)

P = <0.0001 (Kruskal-Wallis test for all groups including control, compensated and decompensated cirrhosis). P = 0.031 (Chi-square test: Control vs. HCV patients).

DISCUSSION:

HCV infection is a serious issue of health, and it plays a very important role in the development of liver diseases. Liver cirrhosis is the fourth most common cause of death in different regions of the world which is mostly attributed to the infection of HCV [2]. Most of the patients of liver diseases are likely to develop Vitamin-D deficiency. Vitamin-D is involved in a large number of complications from mild to severe nature [10]. About 93.0% incidence of deficiency Vitamin-D has been stated in the chronic diseases of the liver, whereas 1/3rd of this accounts to be a deficit of severe nature [11]. This current research work shows 76.50% of sub-optimal Vitamin-D levels in the patients of HCV infection (37.30% deficit & 39.20% insufficient) as compared to the group of healthy controls. These findings are strongly associated with the published information for the deficiency of Vitamin-D in patients suffering from liver complications. Kumar discovered sub-optimal Vitamin-D level in 80.0% of patients of liver cirrhosis [12].

In one other research work from Islamabad conducted by Hamid discovered that 78.0% of 120 patients of liver cirrhosis due to HCV infection were suffering from inadequate Vitamin-D levels [13]. However, opposite to those results, previous studies stated 90.0% of patients were suffering from low Vitamin-D levels (31.0% with deficiency & 59.0% with insufficiency) [14]. One most important factor for the contribution of the low level of Vitamin-D is less exposure of these patients to sunlight [15]. Levels of Vitamin-D displayed an inverse association with high sever conditions of the diseases of liver as 55.20% patients of decompensated cirrhosis were suffering from the deficiency of Vitamin-D in comparison with the 13.60% patients of compensated cirrhosis (Figure-2). These results state that levels of Vitamin-D are the main contributors to the clinical courses of infection because of HCV. Vitamin-D has involvement in different anti-inflammation activities. So, Vitamin-D decreases the HCV core antigen and assembly of virus particles. Deficiency

of Vitamin-D deficiency may also cause enhanced viral load, enhanced inflammation and excessive liver damage [16].

Vidot stated that inefficiency of Vitamin-D was not correlated with the chronic diseases of the liver and associated complications [17]. Similarly, Basile was also unable to find any association between HCV infection and level of Vitamin-D [18]. The role of supplementation of Vitamin-D is not well clear as there are inconsistent results in the evaluation of the association between supplementation of Vitamin-D and other treatment options against these viral infections [19]. We found 39.20% insufficiency of Vitamin-D in patients of HCV. Ladero recorded 40.0% insufficient levels in his samples [20]. Mandorfer, in his research work, stated 57.0% insufficient level of Vitamin-D in his studied population. One other research work conducted on a large sample size by Riaz for the determination of the incidence rate of deficiency of Vitamin-D in our country Pakistan stated that most of the population of our country is suffering from a deficiency of Vitamin-D [21]. A large amount of the factors can be accountable for the heterogeneity in sub-optimal levels of Vitamin-D, including body mass index, dietary habits and racial differences. There are some limitations of this research work as the size of the sample of this research work was very low. This research work is a single-center study. The duration of this research work was very small. There is a need for further research works on large sample size involving multi-centers and for long durations to define the role of deficiency of Vitamin-D in the pathogenesis of various complications.

CONCLUSION:

The results of this research work concluded that 76.50% of patients of HCV infection were present with sub-optimal levels of Vitamin-D. There was an association of the Vitamin-D deficiency with the severity of liver diseases. There was a high frequency of the patients having Vitamin-D lack in d-HCV groups in comparison with the patients in the c-HCV group. We also found the insufficiency of Vitamin-D in subjects of the control group. So, it is much important to estimate the level of Vitamin-D along with the HCV screening test. The supplements of Vitamin-D and modifications in the lifestyle can improve the status of Vitamin-D in the general public, delay the progression of liver disease in the patients of HCV infection; there is need of more research works with large sample size to consolidate the findings of this research work.

REFERENCES:

1. GBD 2013: Global Burden of Diseases, Injuries, and Risk Factors. 2013.

2. Averhoff FM, Glass N, Holtzman D. Global burden of hepatitis C: Considerations for healthcare providers in the United States. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2012;55(Suppl 1): S10-S15. doi:10.1093/cid/cis36
3. Keane JT, Elangovan H, Stokes RA, Gunton JE. Vitamin-D and the Liver-Correlation or Cause? *Nutrients.* 2018;10(4):496-514. doi: 10.3390/nu10040496
4. Holick MF, Binkley NC, Bischoff-Ferrari HA, Gordon CM, Hanley DA, Heaney RP, et al. Evaluation, treatment, and prevention of Vitamin-D deficiency: An Endocrine Society clinical practice guideline. *J Clin Endocr Metab.* 2011;96(7):1911-1930. doi:10.1210/jc.2011-0385
5. Pierret L, Suppa M, Gandini S, Del Marmol V, Gutermuth J. Overview on Vitamin-D and sunbed use. *J Eur Acad Dermatol.* 2019;33(Suppl 2):28-33. doi:10.1111/jdv.15316
6. Heaney RP, Recker RR, Grote J, Horst RL, Armas LA. Vitamin-D(3) is more potent than Vitamin-D(2) in humans. *J Clin Endocr Metab.* 2011;96(3):447-452. doi:10.1210/jc.2010-2230
7. Maan MA, Hussain F, Jamil M. Prevalence and risk factors of HIV in Faisalabad, Pakistan -A retrospective study. *Pak J Med Sci.* 2014;30(1):32-35. doi:10.12669/pjms.301.4176
8. Reda R, Abbas AA, Mohammed M, El Fedawy SF, Ghareeb H, El Kabarity RH, et al. The Interplay between Zinc, Vitamin-D and, IL-17 in Patients with Chronic Hepatitis C Liver Disease. *J Immunol Res.* 2015; 2015:1-11. doi: 10.1155/2015/846348.
9. Glendenning P, Noble JM, Taranto M, Musk AA, McGuinness M, Goldswain PR, et al. Issues of methodology, standardization and metabolite recognition for 25-hydroxyVitamin-D when comparing the DiaSorin radioimmunoassay and the Nichols Advantage automated chemiluminescence protein binding assay in hip fracture cases. *Ann Clin Biochem.* 2003; 40:546-551.
10. Chen EQ, Bai L, Zhou TY, Fe M, Zhang DM, Tang H. Sustained suppression of viral replication in improving Vitamin-D serum concentrations in patients with chronic hepatitis B. *Sci Rep.* 2015;5:15441-15449. doi: 10.1038/srep15441
11. Hoan NX, Khuyen N, Binh MT, Giang DP, Van Tong H, Hoan PQ, et al. Association of Vitamin-D deficiency with hepatitis B virus-related liver diseases. *BMC Infect Dis.* 2016;16(1):507-515. doi: 10.1186/s12879-016-1836-0
12. Kumar V, Yadav AK, Lal A, Kumar V, Singhal M, Billot L, et al. A randomized trial

- of Vitamin-D supplementation on vascular function in CKD. *J Am Soc Nephrol.* 2017;28(10):3100-3108. doi:10.1681/ASN.2017010003
13. Hamid S, Faheem M, Ambreen S, Tirmizi A, Umar M. Comparison of Vitamin-D deficiency and magnitude of its severity in cirrhotic and non-cirrhotic patients with chronic hepatitis C in a tertiary care hospital Rawalpindi, Pakistan. *RMJ.* 2017;42(3):281-285.
 14. Ahmed F. Prevalence of Vitamin-D Deficiency among non-cirrhotic Pakistani Patients with Chronic Viral Hepatitis and Non-alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease. *J Liver: Dis Transplant* 2016; 4: 2. doi:10.4172/2325-9612.1000129
 15. Lim LY, Chalasani N. Vitamin-D deficiency in patients with chronic liver disease and cirrhosis. *Curr Gastro enterol Rep.* 2012;14(1):67-73. doi: 10.1007/s11894- 011-0231-7.
 16. Gayama V, Mandal AK, Khalid, Mukhtar O, Gill A, Garlapati P, et al. Association between Vitamin-D levels and treatment response to direct-acting antivirals in chronic hepatitis C: A real-world study. *Gastroenterol Res.* 2018;11(4):309-316. doi: 10.14740/gr1072w
 17. Vidot H, Potter A, Cheng R, Allman-Farinelli M, Shackel N. Serum 25-hydroxy Vitamin-D deficiency and hepatic encephalopathy in chronic liver disease. *World J Hepatol.* 2017; 9:510–518. doi: 10.4254/wjh. v9.i10.51
 18. Basile U, Napodano C, Pocino K, Barini A, Marinom M, Santini SA, et al. Lack of association between Vitamin-D status and free light chains profile with different chronic HCV-related liver and extrahepatic disorders. *Eur Rev Med Pharmacol Sci.* 2019;23(19):8506-8514. doi: 10.26355/eurev_201910_19164
 19. Huang JF, Ko YM, Huang CF, Yeh ML, Dai CY, Hsieh MH, et al. 25-Hydroxy Vitamin-D suppresses hepatitis C virus replication and contributes to the rapid virological response of treatment efficacy. *Hepatol Res.* 2017; 47:1383- 1389. doi: 10.1111/hepr.12878
 20. Belle A, Gizard E, Conroy G, Lopez A, Bouvier-Alias M, Rouanet S, et al. 25-OH Vitamin-D level has no impact on the efficacy of antiviral therapy in naïve genotype 1 HCV-infected patients. *United European Gastroenterol J.* 2017; 5:69-75. doi: 10.1177/2050640616640157
 21. Ladero JM, Torrejon MJ, Sanchez-Pobre P, Suarez A, Cuenca F, Orden Vdl, et al. Vitamin-D deficiency and Vitamin-D therapy in chronic hepatitis C. *Ann Hepatol.* 2013;12(2):199-204. doi: 10.1016/S1665-2681(19)31357-2